

Spectrophotometric Studies on Nitro-alizarin and Purpurin Complexes with some Rare-earth Salts

S.M.F. Rahman, Naseer Ahmad and Jamil Ahmad

Thorium sulphate, Uranyl sulphate, Gadolinium chloride and Dysprosium chloride react with 3-nitro-alizarin and purpurin (1 : 2 : 4-Trihydroxy anthraquinone) forming dark brown and red complexes, have been studied in continuation with our previous works¹, spectrophotometrically using Vosburgh and Cooper² method of wave length selection, Job's method³ of continuous variation and molar ratio method of Yoe and Jones⁴. Complexes of Gadolinium and Dysprosium chlorides with that of Nitroalizarin and Purpurin were isolated, analysed and formulae suggested.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thorium sulphate (A.R. B.D.H.) and uranyl sulphate (Chemistry Division, Bhaba Research Centre, India) were used in preparing their solutions in ethanol. A known volume of Thorium sulphate was evaporated to dryness and dissolved in distilled water. Thorium was precipitated as oxalate, ignited, weighed as ThO₂ and the strength of the solution was calculated⁵.

The strength of the uranyl sulphate⁶ was determined by evaporating a known volume of its ethanolic solution to dryness, dissolving the residue in water, precipitating uranium as (NH₄)₂-U₂O₇, igniting and weighing as U₃O₈. The solutions of gadolinium and dysprosium were standardised as mentioned earlier⁷.

Vosburgh and Cooper method of wave length selection was employed with $2 \times 10^{-4}M$, $1.6 \times 10^{-4}M$ and $1 \times 10^{-4}M$ solutions of gadolinium and dysprosium chlorides.

Job's method of continuous variations was done with various concentrations as represented in the curves. (1a, 1b).

1. J. Ahmad, N. Ahmad and S. M. F. Rahman; *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 444; 1967, **44**, 485, 1968, **45**, 531.
2. W. C. Vosburgh and G. R. Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
3. P. Job, *Compt. rend.*, 1925, **180**, 928.
5. J. H. Yoe and A. L. Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, III.
5. A. I. 'Vogel, Quantitative Chemical Analysis', Longmans, Green and London, 1955, p. 471.
6. *Ibid.*, p. 470.
7. J. F. Spencer, "The metals of the rare-earths" Longmans, Green and Co., London, 1919, pp.

Molar ratio method was adopted to confirm the results of Job's method for this two sets of experiments were performed. In one set the volume of the metal ion was kept constant and varied amount of the dye was added, and in the second set of experiments the

volume of the dye was kept constant and varied amount of metal ions were added. Results were found to be in agreement with those obtained by Job's method. [Various concentrations of the solution were used as represented by the curves 2a, 2b, 2c and 2d.]

Lamberts and Beer's Law was found to hold good for 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 (metal : dye) in the concentration range of 0.33×10^{-5} — $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, 0.25×10^{-5} — $3.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ and 0.2×10^{-5} — $2.5 \times 10^{-5} M$ for gadolinium and dysprosium complexes with purpurin. In the case of nitroalizarin complexes with gadolinium and dysprosium the validity of Lambert and Beer's Law was found to be in the conc. range of 0.5×10^{-5} — $0.8 \times 10^{-4} M$ for the ratio 1 : 2 (metal : dye).

The complexes of purpurin and nitroalizarin with that of gadolinium and dysprosium were prepared, and analysed as mentioned in our previous publications¹.

TABLE I

Results of Analysis
(3-nitro-alizarin complexes)

	Metal	C	H	N	Cl
1. <i>Gadolinium Complex</i> :					
Calculated for $(C_{14}H_6O_8N)_2$ GdCl	20.64	44.18	1.58	3.68	4.66
Value observed	20.62	44.00	1.76	3.66	4.65
2. <i>Dysprosium Complex</i> :					
Calculated for $(C_{14}H_6O_8N)_2$ DyCl	21.21	43.86	1.56	3.65	4.63
Value observed	21.22	43.81	1.72	3.64	4.62

TABLE 1 (Contd.)

Purpurin Complexes

1. <i>Gadolinium Complex</i> :					
Calculated for $(C_{14}H_7O_5)_2$ GdCl	22.20	47.83	1.99	—	5.07
Value observed	22.18	47.68	2.11	—	5.03
2. <i>Dysprosium Complex</i> :					
Calculated for $(C_{14}H_7O_5)_2$ DyCl	22.95	47.45	1.97	—	5.01
Value observed	22.92%	47.30	2.01	—	4.98

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Vosburgh and Cooper method exhibited maximum absorption at $520\text{ m}\mu$ for nitro-alizarin complexes of thorium, uranium, gadolinium and dysprosium and at $540, 575, 540$ and $545\text{ m}\mu$ for their purpurin complexes respectively. Job's method of continuous variations at the corresponding wave length of maximum absorption yielded a molar ratio of 1 : 1 for thorium and uranium complexes of purpurin and nitroalizarin. It gave a molar ratio of 1 : 2 (metal : dye) for the complexes of gadolinium and dysprosium with nitroalizarin and purpurin. These ratios were confirmed by two sets of molar ratio method. On the basis of the results of analysis the following formulae $(C_{14}H_6O_6N)_2$ GdCl, $(C_{14}H_6O_6N)_2$ DyCl, $(C_{14}H_7O_5)_2$ GdCl and $(C_{14}H_7O_5)_2$ DyCl may be suggested for nitroalizarin and purpurin complexes.

Department of Chemistry,
Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh.

Received February 5, 1968